

HERBAL EXPECTORANT SYRUP FROM *ALLIUM CEPA* L. (LILIACEAE) AND *ERIOBOTRYA JAPONICA* LINDL. (ROSACEAE): FORMULATION AND EVALUATION

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ABSTRACT

Climate change today is one of the main contributors to health emergencies worldwide. Through several mechanisms, it causes respiratory illness, including coughing, in millions of people. In Madagascar, despite the availability of modern medicines, over 60 % of the population use plant-based remedies to treat cough, particularly in rural areas. Therefore, there is an urgent need to develop safe and effective therapeutic options for treating cough as alternative to existing medications. The aim of this study is to review and improve the practice of traditional medicine to integrate it into the official healthcare system. Based on the concept of phytotherapy, this research involves formulating an herbal expectorant syrup from simple, inexpensive and non-toxic ingredients according to the standards required for natural products. Thus, *Allium cepa* and *Eriobotrya japonica* Lindl were chosen as active ingredients due to cough-relieving properties described in traditional medicine. The result is a prototype of a developed, non-toxic herbal syrup with physicochemical properties that meet the standards of the European Pharmacopoeia. However, preclinical tests are still needed to assess the syrup's spectrum activity and mechanism of action before its integration into the public health field.

Keywords: *Allium Cepa*, *Eriobotrya Japonica*, Cough, Syrup, Expectorant, Formulation.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is an established historical fact that, for thousands of years, plants served as a source for therapeutic agents for human beings. In recent years, there has been a surge in interest surrounding the use of Ayurvedic medicine for medicinal purpose (1). From a global perspective, there is an observable shift towards the utilization of herbal medicine, as the dangers and shortcomings of modern medicine become increasingly evident. The World Health Organisation (WHO) reported that 80 % of the emerging world's population relies on traditional medicine for therapy (2). In many parts of Africa, including Madagascar, traditional healers who use medicinal plants are often the most accessible and affordable health source for local communities. Sometimes, they are the only option (3).

Nowadays, people all over the world are exposed to a high level of air pollution. This leads to an increase in coughs associated with acute and chronic conditions affecting people of all ages. This general public health problem is a concern in Madagascar. The use of coal and wood as fuel is common in more than 95 % of households (4). This practice contributes to indoor air pollution, and increases the risk of respiratory illnesses (5).

The successful treatment of cough is contingent upon two factors. Firstly, the treatment must address and regulate the underlying causes of the cough. Secondly, the treatment must desensitize the pathways associated with the cough (6). The specific treatment approach is determined by the function of the cough. In instances where an underlying disease is indicated, treatment should be directed towards its control, prevention, or elimination. In such circumstances, the utilization of expectorants is recommended for not only the alleviation of cough symptoms but also for the prevention of more severe complications.

This study presents the formulation of a new herbal cough syrup containing *Allium cepa* (L) and *Eriobotrya japonica* Lindl. These are food plants but many manuscripts attribute medicinal virtues to them. Their constituents have been extensively studied, several original and review articles have been published on their pharmacological effects. But the aim of this article is to present the galenic formulation of an expectorant syrup made from a combination of leaves and bulb extracts, meticulously designed to optimize efficacy.

The formulation process is a precise and meticulous undertaking. It involves the judicious selection of ingredients, and the execution of precise calculations. These elements are essential for ensuring safety, quality, and efficacy of the final product.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Selection of Herbal ingredients

2.1.1 *Allium cepa* (onion bulb)

Allium cepa is one of the most widely consumed and cultivated vegetable crops on the planet (7). The onion bulb, with its characteristic flavor, is the third most essential horticultural spice, with a substantial commercial value (8). Onion is considered to be one of the oldest cultivated vegetables, and was mentioned in several ancient scriptures. Various studies have examined the biological and chemical properties of this plant. A wide range of phytoconstituents including phenolic acid, flavonoids, anthocyanins, and thiopropyl S-oxide (a volatile sulfide), have been identified in onion bulb (9, 10, 11, 12).

The bulb of *Allium cepa* is highly valued for its therapeutic properties. Recent studies also attempted to reveal that it is anthelmintic, antimicrobial, antifungal, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antiseptic, antispasmodic, carminative, diuretic, expectorant, febrifuge, hypoglycaemic, hypotensive, lithontripic, stomachic, tonic and anti-asthmatic agent (13, 14, 15, 16). People have used onion bulb as a food remedy for a very long time (from ancient Egypt). It is known to treat many chronic diseases and has other healing properties (17, 18). In Malagasy traditional medicine, the onion is particularly used to treat symptoms like runny eyes and nose.

2.1.2 *Eriobotrya japonica* (Loquat leaves)

Eriobotrya japonica Lindl., commonly known as loquat, is a subtropical fruit tree native to China. It has a variety of uses and potential health benefits. The plant is valued for its fruit, leaves, and other parts, which are rich in bioactive compounds like phenolics and terpenoids. The various organs of the loquat tree have been utilized in traditional Chinese medicine for the treatment of a wide range of ailments, including angina, pain, allergies, diabetes, cough, chronic bronchitis and other diseases (19).

Studies indicated potential antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, and cytotoxic property with loquat leaf extract (20, 21, 22). It contains many antioxidants, anti-inflammatory, and antibacterial compounds. Scientific research has demonstrated that the phytonutritional composition of different organs exhibits considerable variation. For instance, loquat leaf and flower are rich in phenolics and triterpenes, while the fruit is rich in sugars, organic acids, carotenoids, flavonoids, phenolic acids, and vitamins. Furthermore, the kernel is a good source of proteins, starch, tannins, and minerals (23, 24).

Figure 1: Onion bulb (*Allium cepa* (L)) and Loquat leaves (*Eriobotrya japonica* Lindl)

2.2 Extraction of active components

The extraction of active components from fresh onion bulb was carried out using a cold maceration method with water- ethanol (80:20) and under the ratio (1/10; w/v). This procedure is particularly useful for

preserving heat-sensitive compounds and is commonly used in various applications, including medicinal herb extraction.

The aqueous extract of *E. japonica* was prepared by decoction with fresh leaves, employing Soxhlation method. This process entails the boiling of plant material in water, a method that facilitates the extraction of heat-stable and water-soluble compounds. For all extraction procedures, the homogenate was filtered using Büchner and filter paper. Subsequently, the filtrate was subjected to a process of evaporation at a temperature of 40° C. Then dry extracts were recovered in powder form, thereby becoming the active ingredients (25, 26).

2.3 Antibacterial activity

The antibacterial activity of plant extracts was examined *in vitro* against bacterial strains gram + (*Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 11632, *Bacillus cereus* ATCC 14579) and gram - (*Escherichia coli* ATCC 8739, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 10145, *Salmonella enterica* ATCC 13076) by the agar disc diffusion method (27). Nutrient Agar was used as the bacteriological medium. It was melted and cooled to 48 -50° C then poured into sterile petri dishes to give a solid plate. The compound of 100 µl (1 mg/disc) of extract was tested. The plates were incubated overnight at 37° C. After that, the antimicrobial spectrum of each extract was subsequently determined for the bacterial species in terms of the Diameters Zone of Inhibition (DZI) around each disc (28). The DZI produced by the agent were compared with those produced by disc reference control antibiotic Neomycin (30 µg/disc). The experimental tests were performed in triplicate and the resulting data were expressed as mean values ± standard deviation (mm ± SD).

2.4 Preparation of the herbal syrup

The preparation of herbal syrups involves after extraction: blending liquid preparation and quality controls. Syrup is formulated by combining herbals extracts (Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients (APIs), sweeteners (sugar), excipients, and additives. The galenic formulation was conducted in strict accordance with the European Pharmacopoeia guidelines (29). Herbal sirup was prepared with *A. cepa* bulb and *E. japonica* leaves extracts. Invert sugar base was prepared by mixing water (480 ml) with granulated sugar (1000 mg). Then, 50 ml of sirup was prepared using aliquots of the quantity used in traditional medicine. Additives were added to it. The syrup was transferred to an amber-colored bottle, closed tightly, and placed in a cool and dry place.

2.5 Quality assurance of syrup produced

Quality assurance is a systematic process to ensure the consistency, safety, stability and microbial purity of herbal formulations (30). This process covers the entire production cycle, from raw material selection to the final product, following established guidelines and standards (31). This is the foundation for preparing a high-quality herbal cough syrup.

2.5.1 Physicochemical parameters evaluation

The developed product has been submitted into physicochemical parameters evaluation. It includ verification of pH, density, specific gravity, viscosity, color, odor, cristalization, sterility, and taste which are essential to ensure consistency and consumer acceptability (32). The Good Manufacturing Practice guidelines clearly state that the herbal syrup must be free from particulate matter, precipitation, or turbidity. They also mandate maintaining within the optimal range (4.5– 6.5) to ensure stability and compatibility with APIs.

2.5.2 Accelerated Stability testing

Accelerated stability studies are conducted under varying environmental conditions to evaluate the product's resistance to degradation (33). Thus, syrup samples were stored at three different temperatures (+4° C, 20° C, 45° C) and observed for changes in color, odor, taste, and turbidity at at 24-hours, 48-hours, and 72-hours intervals over three months.

2.5.3 Freeze Thaw cycling testing

The Freeze Thaw cycling test was conducted. The vials were kept alternately at 40° C and 4° C for 24 hours each, and shaken everyday for 5 minutes on a touch type vortex mixer every day. Two vials of formulation were taken, one of which was kept at 40° C and the other at 4° C for first day. Then, they underwent temperature cycling and shaking as described. After 7-7 such cycles at 4° C and 40° C (alternately), the vials were observed to check turbidity and precipitation, if any.

2.5.4 Sterility testing

Sterility testing was necessary to determine if the formulations met the criteria for acceptance of microbiological quality. The procedures indicated by the European Pharmacopoeia were followed for microbiological control of non-sterile products (34, 35). It guarantees the product is free from bacterial and fungal contamination.

In this study, syrup sterility test was conducted by preparing a 1/10 dilution of the product to be tested in Peptone broth. And, 1 ml of this dilution was spread in Sabouraud agar. Then, plates were incubated at 37° C during 48 hours to look for any growth by total viable count (TVC) assessments.

2.5.5 Acute oral toxicity test

The acute toxicity study of the herbal syrup was carried out according to the guidelines (423, 425) of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) as mentioned by Rakotoarisoa *et al.* (2021). The process was performed on Swiss albino mice, procured from animal house of IMVAVET (Institut Malgache des Vaccins Vétérinaire), as per the standard reported method (36).

Healthy active mice weighing between 22-27g of both sexes were selected and divided into five groups containing five animals in each group. The median lethal dose (LD₅₀) was calculated as the geometric mean of the dose that did not produce mortality and the highest dose that produced mortality where there was mortality but estimated to be above the highest dose exposure if no mortality was recorded.

III. RESULTS

All the results are expressed as mean ± standard error mean. The test "T" of Student was used to evaluate the significance of the differences in the means, and the software "R studio". The values of p lower than 0.05 were regarded as statistically significant.

3.1 Extraction yield of APIs

Extraction yield of APIs in onion bulb (*A. cepa*) and loquat leaves (*E. japonica*) are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Characteristics and extraction yield of APIs

Plants	Extraction yield (%)	Form	Color
<i>Allim cepa</i> (bulb)	9.60	Solid	Brown
<i>Eriobotrya japonica</i> (leaves)	10.71	Solid	Brown

3.2 Antimicrobial activity of the plant extracts

The antimicrobial activity of the plant extracts was obtained from the diameter of the halos tested against bacterial strains (Table. 2).

Table 2: Diameter Zone of Inhibition of *A. cepa* (bulb) and *E. japonica* (leaves)

Test bacteria	Diameter Zone of Inhibition (mm) of 100 µl (1mg/disc)		
	Bulb extract	Leaves extract	Neomicin (30 µg/disc)
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> ATCC 11632	13 ± 0	14 ± 0	21 ± 0.6
<i>Bacillus cereus</i> ATCC 14579	10 ± 0.5	11 ± 0	22 ± 0
<i>Escherichia coli</i> ATCC 8739	11 ± 0	10 ± 0.6	21 ± 0.6
<i>Salmonella enterica</i> ATCC 13076	9 ± 0.3	10 ± 0.2	23 ± 0.3
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> ATCC 10145	9 ± 0.5	9 ± 0	26 ± 0

Mean ± SD

Plant extracts have shown antimicrobial properties. *Staphylococcus aureus* was the most sensitive bacteria. The results conclusively demonstrated the potential efficacy of both plants (*A. cepa* and *E. Japonica*) against bacterial infections.

3.3 Galenic formulation and quality controls

More than tests are carried out to determine the most suitable formula. Evaluation parameters of the herbal sirup are show in Table 3.

Table 3: Physico-chemical and organoleptic parameters of developed herbal syrup

Physico-chemical parameters	Results	Organoleptic characters	Results
Density	1.26	Color	Brownish-Yellow
pH	4.37	Taste	Sweet
Viscosity(cp)	3.60	Odor	Good
Specific gravity	0.6576	Appearance	Clear
Clarity	Clear solution	Cristallisation	Absence
Stability	Stable at room temperature (20 °C)		
Sterility	No proliferation of germs		
Precipitation	No precipitation		

The characteristics about the herbal syrup developed is as follows (Figure. 2).

Composition:
 Plant extracts (*Allium cepa*, *Eriobotrya japonica*)2 %
 Sodium benzoate.....0.2 %
 Excipients.....QS

Posology : Adult :one teaspoon, 1-5 times a day
 Kids (not before 3 years) : half a teaspoon, 1-5 times a day
 Shake well before use

Uses:
 Effective expectoration
 Calming effect
 Deep rapidly restores lung function

Contraindications and Precautions :
 Not for use pregnancy or by individuals with severe liver or kidney disease.

Storage instruction :
 Store in a cool, dry place, away from direct sunlight.

Figure 2: Characteristics and Instructions of use of the herbal syrup

Our outcomes show that the formulated herbal syrup is clear without particles, no turbidity, no precipitation, and sweet in taste. The pH is acceptable for oral use. The viscosity is also fine for storage.

The stability test shows no significant changes between 4° C and 20° C. The product’s organoleptic properties remained consistent, showing no noticeable variations, confirming its stability at moderate temperature conditions. However, when stored at 45° C, a slight change in color and turbidity was observed after 48 hours, with a minor increase in turbidity at 72 hours. This suggests that higher temperatures can impact syrup stability.

In addition, there was no microbiological growth in any of the cultures during the period of the study. None of the samples of the formulations were contaminated during study period.

3.4 Acute oral toxicity test

The safety of the herbal syrup was confirmed through an acute oral toxicity test. The study definitively showed that doses ranging from 5 mg/kg to 5 000 mg/kg did not result in the death of any animals until 72 hours of observation (Table 4). They remain active and alert and there are no symptoms of toxicity. According to OECD guidelines, this product is safe and non-toxic (LD₅₀ > 5 000mg/Kg).

Table 4: Acute oral toxicity result

N°	Group Test	Dose (mg/kg of bodyweight)	Mortality (72 hours), n=5
1	Formulated syrup	5 mg/kg	(0/5)
2	Formulated syrup	50 mg/kg	(0/5)
3	Formulated syrup	500 mg/kg	(0/5)
4	Formulated syrup	2000 mg/kg	(0/5)
5	Formulated syrup	5000 mg/kg	(0/5)
6	Control group	1 ml	(0/5)

IV. DISCUSSION

The use of complementary and alternative medicines is common in many countries around the world. Herbal medicines are still used by 75- 80 % of the world population for primary health care. They are culturally acceptable, compatible with human beings, and have fewer side effects (37). The formulation of herbal drugs plays a pivotal role in bridging traditional knowledge with modern pharmaceutical sciences.

According to the present study, it was concluded that the prepared herbal expectorant syrup has good physical characteristics and exhibits good accelerated stability. The product's appearance was undeniably attractive, with its appealing color, odor and taste. Syrup is used to treat many ailments and alleviate symptoms of disease. This herbal syrup is better than over-the-counter medications because it is safe and has no negative side effects. We performed an acute oral toxicity test. This test definitively determines whether there are any toxic effects. Our results conclusively show that it is safe for human use as a drug because no animal exhibited the signs and symptoms of toxicity. So, this new herbal syrup is effective in treating coughs in children and adults. It works by increasing antioxidant, expectorant and decongestant properties of the plants that are found in the respiratory tract. This research successfully concluded that this syrup made from *A. cepa* bulb and *E. japonica* leaves shows its maximum effect and decreases the severity of cough. Also, preparations have a strong potential to combat pathogenic bacteria and can be utilized as an antimicrobial agent to treat a variety of infectious disorders. By incorporating advanced techniques in drug delivery, standardization, and quality control, the therapeutic potential of herbal formulations can be significantly enhanced.

V. CONCLUSION

The present study helps to developed effective, safe and simple herbal syrup containing onion bulb and loquat extracts. This result demonstrates the promising physicochemical properties and quality. It can also be concluded that the synergic combination of these herbal ingredients enhances the expectorant syrup benefits, offering a natural and effective remedy for cough. The research highlights that *Allium cepa* and *Eriobotrya japonica* components in herbal syrup formulation are effective for managing cough conditions. These formulations are not only effective in addressing chronic and lifestyle-related diseases but also align with the growing demand for natural and sustainable healthcare solutions. Even so, clinical trials are needed of future concern.

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